

Political Independence without Economic Independence: a Survey of Third World Economies

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ABSTRACT

Without doubt, economy is among the determinant factors of states' existence, citizens' welfare and general development; without vibrant supporting economy, states and individuals' visions and missions would continue to be distant objectives if not unattainable. However, historical approach and political analysis- the two inextricable phenomena could be relied upon as the guiding principle in order to define states and understand states economy in the third world and how it was affected as a result of several underlying issues that continue to shape and direct the course of the economy of the states in the third world. It would be in line with the aforementioned scene that this research would focus and delve as to show and justify with facts as to why third world states continue to grapple with economic uncertainty, stagnation, backwardness and crisis in general to the extent they remain as conduits supporting economically developed states acting as metropolis despite been politically independent for decades.

Keywords: States, Colonialism, Independence, Imperialism and Capitalism

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INTRODUCTION

Throughout the existence of mankind on this planet from the early ages to medieval and up to the contemporary world often being referred to as Renaissance Age in the history of civilizations, states exist although with different dimensions as regards to their purpose, composition and philosophy with respect to the type of society they manage as

government. In the light of this statement, states exist and serve its duties and roles base on the existing economic capacity of the state. Therefore, the sates and economy are interwoven and in some instances the latter compliments the former.

However, the economy of itself of many third world states had been on the radar of external forces which were skillfully planted long time ago, and had grown

to maturity to the point where the fruits are now enjoyed not by the very soil where it was planted, but by the far and distant influence thereby creating a cog on the wheel of the states concerned and their economy as well.

Considering the above scenario, it is vividly clear that third world states and their economy were in theory sovereign and independent, but technically skewed in favour of the metropolitan states (Western states) thus leaving the peripheral states (third world states) in squalor through invisible force and self centred policies in favour of the metropolis states.

DEFINITION OF CONCEPTS: Political Independence, Economic Independence and Third World Economies/States,

Political Independence: political independence was subjected to various interpretations; contemporarily it was defined as ‘... independence in relation to a portion of the globe is the right to exercise therein, to the exclusion of any other state, the functions of a state’.¹ By this proposition, it simply denotes the existence of an organized body which operates through its agencies and capable of determining its internal and external affairs without being directed by any other authority from another organization called state.

Other elements attached to states as features of political independence include: population no matter how small or large, territory i.e boundary/demarcation, sovereign i.e capable of determining its own affairs, and a government that manages all other sectors as state organs and machineries.

Economic Independence: by this it means building an economy that progresses without depending on others. If this is achieved by a state, it guarantees independent development of the country and nation so also economic stability.² This does not mean building a closed economy or simply ruling out exchange of ideas with other countries, but rather it implies that obtaining what is lacking or is short of

through exchanges and cooperation with other counties.

By this way, the potentials of the state is harnessed and developed through peoples talent capable of moving the country forward economically³ and stand out and economically independent *per se*.

Third World Economies/States: third world states or countries so to say was a term that was coined in the period from 1945-1990's to technically refer to states/countries that are neither with the socialists nor the capitalists countries. But, the economic cum political definition was widened as to describe countries with substandard, underdeveloped, or underperforming conditions in certain fields, which are in great need of development. They are identified by and fall under the categories with poor economy and non human development in terms of political and civil liberties. Examples of these countries include: Burma, Libya, Sudan, Iraq, Syria, and Zimbabwe⁴ among others just to mention but a few. It is important to note that most of these countries are located in Africa, Asia, Latin America and Parts of Eastern Europe.

External Influence/Colonialism: in this research work it donates a state or a country that had experience colonialism and hence, its socio-economic policies continue to be guided by such policies in the post-colonial age which continue to create unequal terms as the main guiding principle of economic policy of the former colony.

STATES: THIRD WORLD STATES BEFORE COLONIALISM

In Africa, Latin America and Asia as well, states exist for centuries before the incursion of foreign powers that later came and dominate the people ways of life through colonial conquests. For instance: in Africa, there were empires of Ghana, Mali and Songhay as far

¹ M. Wood., "Independence", *Princeton Encyclopedia of Self Determination*, Princeton, Princeton Univ. 2021

² A. M Muhammad., Economic Independence of DPRK, the cable news, august 10th, 2021

³. Ibid.

⁴ See S. Williams., What is the Definition of a Third World Country? Borgen Project, march 18, 2018 See also Countries of the third World, available on https://www.nationsonline.org/oneworld/third_world.htm Accessed on 22nd December, 2021

back as 8th to 17th centuries A.D,⁵ Borno Empire that lasted for almost 1000 years,⁶ Buganda state,⁷ Bunyoro kingdom,⁸ and the Sokoto caliphate which was conquered in 1903 by the British imperialists.⁹

The economy of these states as it were, was characterized as self generating and self sustaining type, in the sense that it capitalizes on the exploitation and development of local resources using indigenous technology and methods to satisfy needs and for exchange purposes i.e trade. For instance, let us discuss the Sokoto caliphate (1804-1903) which is now in Nigeria as a classical case study during its existence as regards to the state and economy.

For in the Sokoto caliphate, the economy was set as all encompassing and fully integrated with each part within the confederate state producing an item in respect of the availability of the resources at reach. For in the main areas within the caliphate capital, each has attain a particular skill of trade that serve the people. Areas as *Majema, Takalmawa, Marina, Masaka, Makera* were areas known to have been producing items as: leather and skin tanners, shoemakers, dyers, woodcarvers/carpenters and blacksmiths respectively. Apart from these items, agricultural produce was spread to distant stations across the capital. For areas around Gwandu, Goronyo, Gandi, Rabah and Kware were classified as *Ribats*¹⁰ not only serving as administrative and defense districts, but also agricultural estates and plantations to

compliment the food needs of the growing caliphate's population.

Also within the political structure of the confederate states of the caliphate (Emirates), there exists elaborate system of trade chiefs representing all occupational groups and trades. Titles as *Sarkin Rafi, Sarkin Noma, Sarkin Kasuwa* and *Tafarki* as titles relating to chief of gardens, chief of farmers, chief of markets and chief of highways respectively.¹¹

Although the community is well structured and empowered socially and economically, there are also other sources of revenue for the caliphate. These are: tithe, poll tax, land tax, booty and surplus i.e the property whose owner is missing, and the property which is ownerless.¹²

In India, before the advent of colonial rule, it has a self sufficient flourishing economy. With the economy purely an agrarian including irrigation farming, as rice and wheat were commonly grown alongside few supporting handicraft industries in the fields of cotton and silk textiles, metals and other precious stone works- the quality of crafts had made India's products not only popular, but also sought after in huge demands in Asia and the world at large.¹³ It was during this eriod that Indians economy was credited as the "Golden Age" or "Gupta Empire Period" which

⁵ J. Ryle et al.,(eds.), *The Sudan Handbook*, London, Boydell & Brewer Ltd, 2011 and Google search "images of Power and Identity" Available at <https://africa.si.edu/exhibits/ipi?westsud.htm> Accessed 19th December,2021.

⁶ H. Vincent., *A History of Borno*, London, HURST Publishers Ltd, 2017 See also M, Kyari., "Borno Under Rabih Fadl Allah, 1893-1900: The Emergence of a Predatory State". In *Paideuma*, Vol. 43, Pp. 281-300

⁷ B. Barkindo et. al., *Africa & Wider World 2: East, Central and Southern Africa Since 1800*, Ibadan, Longman Nigeria Plc, 1992, Pp. 43-72

⁸ A. R. Dunbar., *A History of Bunyoro-Kitara*, Oxford, OUP, 1965, Pp. 10-81. See also The Open University, Knowledge Media Institute, CORE, United Kingdom for more details on *The History of Bunyoro*.

⁹ See O. Ikime, *The Fall of Nigeria: The British Conquest*, London, Heinemann Educational Books, 1977. See also in A. Y. Jiwon., *The Sultanate of Sokoto (Sokoto Caliphate)* Available at BLACKPAST.ORG Accessed 22nd November, 2021.

¹⁰ . M. B., Sallau, "Ribats and the Development of Planatations in the Sokoto Caliphate: A Case Study of Fanisau",in *African Economic History* 34(34):23 DOI:10.2307/25427025

¹¹ . See Y.B Usman., *The Transformation of Katsina, 1400-1883 The Emergence and Overthrow of the Sarauta System and the Establishment of the Emirate*, Zaria, ABU Press, 1981 for more information on the nature of states formative stages in the history of Hausa land based on the relation of occupational groups as a kind of symbiotic relations in many early settlements that later emerged as states..

¹² Kabiru Sulaiman Tsafe the State and Economy in the Sokoto Caliphate: Policies and Practices in the Metropolitan Districts, c. 1804-1903, 1992, Ph.D Thesis, Dept. of History, Ahmadu Bello University, zaria, Pp.121-131

¹³ . British Colonial Rule: India Before and After Colonization Available at <https://www.toppr.com/guides/economics/indian-economy-on-the-eve-independence/british-colonial-rule/> Accessed 20th November,2021

was marked by advancements in trade, masonry, arts, music among other remarkable achievements.¹⁴

In Latin America, the once known empire states of Inca, Aztecs and Maya were flourishing states, with an elaborate system of government and economy that supports the state as independent entities.

For Incas economy was purely based on communalism; where the main unit of production is land which was worked jointly in the cultivation communes known as *Ayylus*.¹⁵ Corn, beans, potatoes and maize were the basic produce. Apart from tilling the lands, each region specializes in other trade, depending on the availability of a particular materials needed or skill involved. Trades and skills in the regions include: road building, textile production, basket weaving, architectural designs and buildings among other trades, as various taxes were exacted to finance states projects in needs such as during famine and drought.

The government at the centre normally collects the entire surplus after local needs were met, and distributed it where it was needed. In this consideration, the citizen necessities as clothing, food, health care and education were provided free for all.¹⁶

COLONIALISM

In this aspect one need to understand what colonialism is and how it was skewed to produce a dependent economy of the third worlds even after it was systematically annihilated and despised globally.

Colonialism is defined ‘as “control by one power over a dependent area or people”.¹⁷ It goes on to further highlight the content and context of the concept as explained in the above quote as: Colonialism “occurs when one nation subjugates another, conquering its population and exploiting it, often while forcing its own language and cultural values upon its people.”¹⁸

¹⁴. See A. Eraly., *The First Spring: Life in the Golden Age of India. Part 1*, India, Penguin Books, Rev.Ed, 2015

¹⁵. Economy of the Inca Empire Available at www.discover-peru.org/inca-economy-society/ Accessed 21/12/2021

¹⁶. “Maya, Aztec and Inca Civilization”, in *Core Knowledge Sequence: History and Geography, no:5* Available at www.coreknowledge.com Accessed 21/12/2021

From the above conception about colonialism as explained, it tersely elucidate the word as it is often used, and the way it was meant to serve as a kind of unequal relation between the exploited and exploiters.

Margaret, Collins, and Webster consider colonialism and defined it as:

A practice or policy of control by one people or power over other people or areas, often by establishing colonies and generally with the aim of economic dominance. In the process of colonization, colonizers may impose their language, economics, and other cultural practices.¹⁹

The above definition succinctly explained the aim of this research work as a kind of imposition of alien rule on a people by a foreign power with the aim of exploiting the resources of the exploited and at the same to undermine the culture of the indigenous population in its entirety.

In Africa, colonialism was stemmed after the Berlin Conference of 1884-5, and each of the European powers carved out their spheres of influence and implement favourable policies on the colonized areas. As Britain, France, Portugal and Belgium were the active European colonizers in Africa during the period under review (from 1880's up).

In West Africa, the French and British colonial policies were directed towards the economy of the colonies. This was aimed at feeding their industries with raw materials and at the same time a readily available market for their output/products. By this, colonial Africa was reduced as a primary producer of raw materials and consumer of European manufactures.

One of the economic policies adopted was the monetization of the economy. Thus, European monies replaced pre-colonial exchange medium. Not only

¹⁷. Erin, Blakemore. “What is Colonialism?” American Monthly magazine, Published by National Geographic Society, February 19, 2019

¹⁸ *Ibid*.

¹⁹ Margaret Kohn, “Colonialism”, Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Stanford, Univ. Press, 2017 and Harper Collins, “Colonialism”, Collins English Dictionary, 2011 Webster’s Encyclopedia Unabridged Dictionary of the English, 1989. Pp. 290-299

that, the European banks as West African Currency Board(W.A.C.B)²⁰ and CFAO²¹ were the sole sources where the monies could be sourced from. Therefore, for one to get the money to pay for imposed tax, he must produce what the European firms need. Items as: groundnut, cotton, cocoa, palm oil, Shea butter and spices were the principal items of the trade. Under this type of relations, the Africans had only one choice i.e to cultivate the needed agricultural produce, as for the price it was the sole responsibility of the approved European buying firms to fix the price of commodities through their agents known as the License Buying Agents (LBA's) to buy from the farmers on behalf of the colonial firms known as the commodities Marketing Boards.²²

On infrastructural development, industrialization and social services, the colonial government did little to develop the colonies. For instance; all railways constructed during colonialism only linked cash crop production areas with the harbours, where they could be exported to the metropolis states. Roads traversed areas where there are available colonial government offices and interests to protect. For the industries, only semi and micro raw materials processing industries were developed, such as ginneries, cocoa processing plants et al. As for education, the colonizers only taught to Africans the rudimentary aspect of it such as reading, writing, arithmetic and Europeans history with little craft skill all included. This was meant to train them fit to serve in the colonial firms as traders and easy recruits to facilitate colonial needs as clerks and messengers. As for the clinics and health services, they only provide skeletal services to the natives.

The consequence of the relationship was that, all African labour was diverted towards cash crops production as against food crops production. This was why there was a widespread hunger during colonialism as diseases of malnutrition became common especially among children known as

Kwashiokor.²³ Also there was massive rural-urban drift as not everyone is able to pay the prescribed taxes imposed, therefore, the best solution is to move to towns and urban areas where there could be jobs so that one may be able to satisfy the taxes and earn a living. Another sad note was the backwardness and death of many indigenous craft industries and local markets, which results in over reliance on foreign materials, tools and technology for agricultural production and other materials needed as well for survival.

In Asia third world states, colonialism did not favour them to some extent. For in India and elsewhere as well, the colonial government only focuses on the exploitation of raw materials and other resources of the areas concerned. Thus, the exploitation formula was re-organization of communities into production estates by using agents known as the *Zamindaris*²⁴ with Jute, cotton, indigo, tea, sugarcane and oilseeds as the main cash crops.

Self sustainability has been waned and commercialization of labour and large scale migration ushered in which led to famine in some areas, unlike in the pre-colonial India, food sufficiency which has now vanished and resulted in deterioration and stagnation- particularly with regard to food production as the *Zamindaris* were ruthless by nature in exacting rents, taxes and surpluses.²⁵

In Latin American states, European colonization and settlement started in about 1500's which changed the structure of the economy and caused lasting effect to their economy and the states till date.

Exports form the bulk of the needs of the colonizers. Due to the availability of resources both natural and mineral, the Latin American states were colonized in earnest by the Spaniards largely then followed by the Portuguese. These European colonizers discovered goldmines in large quantities in Technotitlan, Cuzco,

²⁰ . The National Archives, Kew. *West African Currency Board*, File no: CO 984

²¹ . CFAO, Edinburgh University Library, Special Collections, Ref: GB COLL-444 Also available on line at <https://archiveshub.jisc.ac.uk/data/gb237-coll-444>

²² J. Robins., *Cotton and Race Across the Atlantic: Britain, Africa, and America, 1900-1920*, Rochester, Univ. Press, 2016, Pp.144-200

²³ C. D. Williams, "The Story of Kwashiokor", in *Nutrition Reviews/Vol. 31/No: 11/ November, 1973*

²⁴ Indian Economy on the Eve of Independence Available on www.toppr.com/guides/economics/indian-economy-on-the-eve-of-independence/ Accessed 23/12/2021 See also Chandreyi, *Tea Gardens and Geographies of Colonial Exploitation*, Wisconsin, Univ. Press, 2021

²⁵ . *Ibid*

Otavalor which today form new Latin American states as Peru, Mexico, Ecuador, Bolivia and Argentina. Therefore, conquest was the tool to get access to such treasures. Thus, in areas controlled by the Spanish, the colonial administration was known as *Conquistadors*²⁶ with a geared economic policy called *Encomiendas*.²⁷ This Policy had some secret clause reservations aimed to empower the colonizers as the courts and other colonial machineries were in favour of the Spanish, and therefore purely alien to the natives. Labour relationship was relied upon, where the natives were made to produce agricultural and forest exports like woods and other luxuries for the colonizers, apart from engaging them in the mining sector.

That was the scenario of colonialism in Latin America which has some similarities in Africa and Asia as was described by Post-colonial African writer Walter Rodney in his book titled 'How Europe Underdeveloped Africa', where he lamented that "colonialism had only one hand- it was a one armed bandit"... he blamed colonialism for laying the foundation of Africa's economic dependency on the international capitalist system.²⁸

INDEPENDENCE

Decolonization as a process towards independence had succeeded in making its imprints on many colonial subjects to the extent that independence was achieved through either passive or active moves i.e violent or non-violent method. Years of colonial oppression and economic backwardness together with external influence against colonialism all combined together to give sense to colonial subjects towards a common struggle and destiny as people and nations as well.

Top of the agitators or nationalists' agenda was the non-inclusion of the indigenous population in the exploitation of their resources for their own benefit. They resented the exploitative policies and system of colonial administration as totally evil and against their development in general.

Some notable personalities in Africa include Kwame Nkrumah of Ghana, Nnamdi Azikiwe of Nigeria, Julius Nyerere of Tanzania. In Latin America, persons as Simon Bolivar, Ernesto Che Guevara just to mention but a few. For Asia, Mahatma Gandhi and Jawarl Harlal Nehru – all these nationalists had common slogan i.e total independence of their states from all colonial vestiges.

More so, the two World Wars I&II (1914-1918 and 1939-1945) and their aftermath, the emergence of the United States as world super power and her repudiation stance to colonial and empire holding, so also the Atlantic Charter of 1941²⁹ which set all people free from the yokes of colonialism. These series of events liberated many third world states in the twentieth century, and that was why it was called a "century of independence" for the third world states.

But, does it mean that the third world states are really independent as they were meant to be both in theory and practice?

INDEPENDENT THIRD WORLD STATES: CAPITALISM AND IMPERIALISM

Despite jubilations and high expectations upon attainment of political independence by the third world states, it was accompanied by uncertainties and dilemmas, as to which type of socio-economic system is suitable and can operate or be adopted in their states.

Also on the part of the erstwhile colonizers, they envisage that if the new independent states are allowed to become developed along any of the socio-economic and political line, they would compete with them in terms of economy, industrialization, military strength et. al. Therefore, the best idea is to continue to wield influence on the third world states by whatever means and thwart their efforts towards any development plan, ideas and agenda through a policy dependency, which define the extent of relations and based on the new formed theory as thus;

²⁶ . C. Minster, "Spain's American Colonies and the Encomienda System", ThoughtCo, Sep. 9, 2021 See also [thoughtco.com/spain-american-colonies-encomienda-encomienda-system-2136545](https://www.thoughtco.com/spain-american-colonies-encomienda-encomienda-system-2136545). Accessed 20/12/2021

²⁷ .Ibid.

²⁸ . Ibid.

²⁹ . See D. Brinkley et. al., *the Atlantic Charter (The World of the Roosevelt's)*, Palgrave, Macmillan, 1994.

... in reinforcing the dependency on the third world states, two important tools are used, they are capital and finance. The dependent nations come to owe the developed nations so much money and capital that is not possible to escape debt, and thereby continuing the dependency for the foreseeable future.³⁰

From the above point expressed, the former colonial administrators and their home governments were determined to continue their dominance over the new independent states, so much that they capitalize on

the state of the poor economy and lack of capital of the new independent third world states, therefore, to over burden them with debt is to continue exploiting them in the process of external debt services at the expense of national development where the capital is much needed. The chart below represents the extent of external debt of under developed economies of the third world from the year 2000-2018.

*Blue Colour: personal remittance received in US\$ *Gray Colour: net official development recorded in US\$
Source: www.cadtm.org Google Search :developing countries caught in the vice Accessed 27/12/2021

The above chart shows that the new politically independent states were caught within the trap of borrowing (debt), without commensurate development records many years after independence. The developed economies were using different terminologies in order to persuade third world states to accept such loans and grants. Such terms as soft loans, grants, waivers and intervention in foreign aids or foreign direct investment (FDI) as the case may be; were some of the common terms. These terms were succinctly digested as: it makes the states to rely on foreign capital to pursue economic and political reforms inwardly by many countries of the third world. These aids and grants, have become the reliable sources of finance to most third world economies, and for this reasons, they were classified as Less Developed States (LDS) whereas, the donor states are

called Developed States (DS). The reliance of country/states on foreign aids will have a negative economic effect in its entirety.³¹

GENERAL OVERVIEW OF THIRD WORLD STATES

The polarization of the world states into classes of the haves and the haves not was defined so often by strong and reliable economy. This makes us to understand why some countries are still poor and underdeveloped and while others continue to grow economically. The study of this paradigm lies in understanding the socio-political relations of the two and the unique features of the third worlds states or developing economies as some apologists want them to believe.

³⁰ . Ashley. C., "Definition and Examples of Dependency Theory", ThoughtCo. Retrieved 12/02/2020 Accessed 27/12/2021

³¹ , C. Micheal et al., "Counting Chickens When They Hatch: Timing and the Effects of Aids on Growth", in *The Economic Journal*, 122(561) 2011, Pp. 589-620

Common characteristics of the third world states are that they depend heavily on mono cultural economy i.e specialize on the production of one single commodity as a means of earning foreign exchange. For instance: Venezuela, Libya and Nigeria got most of their wealth from crude oil sales in the international markets. It accounted more than 65% of Nigeria's annual revenue to the government;³² for Venezuela, oil comprises of 95% exports and 25% GDP³³ and for Libya, it represents about 69% of export earnings and this contributed to about 60% of the total GDP of the country.³⁴ Based on these percentages as regards to the contributions of oil and gas to the economy, the economy itself can be described as is in a fragile state - when oil prices are high, they enjoy good economic fortunes, and when prices drop, economic disaster sets in generally.

Secondly, they have larger populations without commensurate opportunities; unlike developed economies. Of the total world population of about 7 billion, the highly industrialized nations classified as G7, do not have larger populations in excess presently and their population may increase by 2030 to about 3.3%; while those of developing countries will be about 20.7%.³⁵ These projected figures are alarming, because as the total world population increases without growth in economic opportunities; so the poverty margin continues to widen, and for that third world countries continue to rely so much on debt to address the imbalance which of course they could not due to poor economic and planning policies.

More so, the population increase will lead to large scale migrations towards more prosperous countries and regions of the world from the third world states. This would no doubt aggravate poverty from the source of migrants as virile young men and women leave their states without investing their energies and resources in their home countries. Though it was envisaged that demographic increases will provide huge opportunities for business and people, large challenges too are expected to arise as billions of people come into existence and join urban ways of life

³² . Nigeria Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative NEITI Available on www.eiti.org/es/implementing_country/32 Accessed on 30/12/2021

³³ . Greg Depersio, How Does the Price of Oil Affect Venezuela's Economy?, *Investopedia*, 25/06/2019(updated)

as migrations from rural to urban cities and areas increase many times as was put forward as:

By 2030, 60% of the world's population will be living in urban areas, compared to today's 53%. In number terms, this means that 1.2 billion people will be leaving the fields to take part in city life. Eight out of ten (82%) people in developed countries and almost 56% of the population in developing countries will live in urban areas.³⁶

With majority of the population adopting city life in the third world states the utilization of their labour and productivity seems to be a distant objective, as the migrants will become excess or surplus talents which may not be realized forever and hence, continue to live in poverty due to their states historical-economic ties with the highly developed worlds that did nothing to set and direct the society towards self sufficiency and economic independence of the third world states.

On another note which has much to do with indirect foreign influence of the developed economies through international organizations and bodies which continue to subjugate the economy of third world states despite being independent politically. Some of these bodies include:

- (a) Commonwealth: being it an organization of former British colonies, it has to some extent continued to influence the economy of its former colonies through interventions with international business cartels. For instance: Crude oil sales and exchange to international markets from the former colonies is constantly under the watchful eyes of Britain. It upholds that such is aimed to protect the interest of her former colonies commodities exchange. But, over years of such intercessions between the former colonies and the international markets, there has never a point in time when Britain openly act to make sure products from its former colonies was being underpaid according to world prices.³⁷

³⁴ OPEC Annual Statistics Bulletin 2021

³⁵ Roland Berger Consultancy, UK, 24 June 2015

³⁶ Roland Berger., *Op. Cit.*,

³⁷See P. Murphy., *The Empire's New Clothes: The Myth of the Commonwealth*, Oxford, OUP, 2018

(b) European Economic Community (EEC)/European Union (EU) Aids: through this agency, the European Economic Community has been pouring so called aids and grants to help poor countries of which the third worlds are the main targeted states. The so called aids were the avenues to explore more areas of economic significance to the European member states, as some of the third worlds are still grappling with political uncertainties, therefore, dealing with uncertain governments in business is risky as governments might be easily unseat due to political instability. And the best way to explore and exploit third world states is to pose as helping friends, while reporting to their home countries the enormous potentialities of the states for possible ways to exploit them.³⁸ Even when decolonization was taking its effects in Africa and elsewhere, there was already a plan to continue to exploit third world states through another union of European states. This was aptly expressed by the leader of Pan-European movement, Richard Coudenhove-Kalergi that:

Africa could provide Europe with raw materials for its industry, nutrition for its population, land for its overpopulation, labour for its unemployed, and markets for its products. "Beyond Eurafica: Encounters in a Globalized World", *Europe Now Journal*, 28/02/2018 Available online at www.europenowjournal.org

From the above it can be seen that, Europe is fully prepared to integrate its society and economy so as to pursue policies common to them no matter the rhetorical chores of the independence granted to the third worlds, and they have succeeded in harmonizing common exploitative policies against non European-third world states. For example: the formation of the European Movement (1948), organization for European Economic Co-operation (1948), the Council of Europe (1949), and finally the the European

Economic Community (1957). These bodies are determined not only to relinquish colonialism, but rather elevate it to an international supranational level globally and they have succeeded to a certain degree till date.³⁹ And as the dictum goes on to state the true nature of such European associations and bodies as:

The European Union must, of course, include its orbit the extensions, dependencies and associated territories of the European Powers in Africa and elsewhere, and must preserve the existing constitutional ties with them...we do not wish to see Africa lost to European influence, culture, trade etc...

So, by whatever policy and standard, the third world were forcibly joined to the whims and caprices of the Europe no matter the amount of efforts made to free themselves from the bondage of Europe's exploitative means and manoeuvres.

(c) United Nations (UN) and its strategies: the UN as an international body has not been fair in its role to third world states. In that, some third world states have been turned into supporting countries of the industrialized worlds under the guise as primary production areas with the support of UN's programmes and subsidiaries, such as the FAO. It was envisaged that through support to food production in the third world states, they may not likely realize their position as supporters of the developed worlds through food production in their countries. Historically, food has never been a problem in many third world states before colonialism, but with the inception of colonialism and forcible intensification of cash cropping system to the detriment of food crops, hunger and starvation set in. So, through assisting in the production of foods to the impoverished nation's population, the

³⁸ . John. Ravenhill, "Review: Equals, Clients, or Dependents? A.C.P Relations with the E.E.C under the Lome Conventions" *The Journal of Modern African Studies*, Vol.25, No. 4, (Dec. 1987), Pp.700-740

³⁹ . Ibid.

psyche of the citizens and the state as well may be directed into thinking that – the UN's FAO food programme is helping matters as regards to their plight (hunger).⁴⁰

CONCLUSION

It is clear from the above facts highlighted and discussed that, the third worlds are nothing both politically and economically rather than instruments in the hands of those who through their mischievous aims and visions in the domination and continuous exploitative policies that were designed to rule economies (third world states) in order to develop their states (developed worlds) and peoples. No doubt that, they (developed states) had tried many times to convince the world it was not economic motive that made them to come out of their lands and start colonizing other states. The reality can be seen as to why in the process they did not maintain mutual economic relationships with the third world states at the time they arrived and left? Secondly, their exploitative policies during colonialism in making the colonized produce what was not required or needed was to negate the states needs, and forced them to rely entirely on foreign products. Thirdly, upon attainment of political independence of the third world states, the developed states merged their businesses and firms into cartels and corporations in order to continue to influence third world states' economy – which in many cases determined how truly independent a state is, and its capacity to determine the destiny of its citizens without interference from any other state or body no matter how big and militarily strong it is.

Therefore, the whole idea of political independence was cloaked under the garb of perception that: the third worlds are free, but in reality, there was only a replacement/substitution of political leadership from alien rule to native rule, the position and status of the economy is still the status quo as during direct control by the alien rulers of the third worlds.

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⁴⁰UN/FAO, "Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations: the State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World". Latest issue: SOFI 2021